

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide for assembling an assessment team

Full resource

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Introduction to the guide

Summary

This guide helps identify the types of expertise, roles and tasks required within a research assessment team. It is particularly useful for individuals responsible for designing, managing, or overseeing the assessment process.

Additionally, the Stakeholder mapping template <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525686> can support the identification of relevant stakeholders involved in a research assessment (RA) process.

For more detailed guidance on the roles and responsibilities of evaluators - aligned with responsible research assessment (RRA) principles - the Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526025> is available.

The checklist for responsible research assessment (RRA) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524455> is a valuable tool for checking many critical points throughout the assessment process.

Guide as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards a more responsible research assessment. Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this guide supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols. It is particularly relevant to the SCOPE phases S (Start) and C (Context).

[SCOPE Framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant in the stages S and C.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Considerations for assembling an assessment team

What is an assessment team?

An assessment team refers to a group of people with the needed expertise to plan and conduct a research assessment process. An assessment team may comprise permanent and rotating professionals from various positions from, for example, the research services, human resources, IT services, or library.

Assessment committees or panels referring to evaluators in organisation-level research assessment exercises are discussed in the

- Institutional assessment process checklist <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526008>

General guidelines for an assessment team

Understanding and being familiarized with guidelines, principles and concepts of RA as well as critical thinking is necessary. Read more about key principles and guidelines in the Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526025>. Ethical guidelines and EDI dimensions such as, for example, career stage, field or discipline, gender, sexual orientation, racial/ethnic origin, socio-economic status, disability and language should always be carefully considered in all RA practices. More about EDI issue in the Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in Research Assessment <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526122>.

Also, as proposed by [Science Europe \(2020\)](#), the involvement of other stakeholders (potential industry partners, for instance) in the design and development of assessment schemes should be considered. In addition, effective communication and coordination for a common understanding of the challenges involved in research assessment is important as well as sharing lessons learnt and good practices between all stakeholders and research organizations to promote the reform of research assessment. And finally, cost and efficiency of RRA processes and all investment of time and effort must be considered carefully especially for processes that rely on most time-consuming qualitative evaluations. Read more: Science Europe Position Statement and Recommendations on Research Assessment Processes (2020), Science Europe, <https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/3twjxim0/se-position-statement-research-assessment-processes.pdf>

Areas of expertise, roles and tasks needed in an assessment process

In all RA processes it is crucial that stakeholders are aware of their responsibilities, roles and tasks. In general, roles can be related to planning, facilitating or implementing assessment. Tasks refer to specific pieces of work. Roles and tasks are closely interconnected and work together to ensure a successful assessment process.

Overall coordination and management of RA must be clearly defined and identifying the many kinds of expertise, roles and tasks needed is useful when compiling an assessment team. Table 1. presents examples of areas of expertise, roles and tasks which may vary depending on the assessment process and organization.

Table 1. Areas of expertise, roles and tasks of a RA process

Examples of expertise	Examples of roles and tasks
Understanding of discipline specific research activities and outputs.	Communication internally and externally
Thematic and contextual knowledge and expertise. Understanding e.g. key concepts and theories in the research field	Project management

Ethical considerations	Resourcing assessment process
Understanding EDI dimensions	Overall coordination and management of an assessment process
Understanding meaning of open and responsible science	Awareness of the stages of the evaluation process and the methodology used
Cross-cultural considerations	Cost-benefit analysis of RRA process
Cultural characteristics of research. Understanding how cultural background can affect especially qualitative research	Quantitative analysis, data quality checks
Understanding the variety of academic career paths and stages	Visualization
Responsible use of metrics and indicators	Facilitating qualitative evaluation, peer review
Wide understanding of impact (societal, economic, scientific)	
Reporting skills, excel skills, visualising skills	
Expertise in evaluating personalities and general working life skills	
Interpersonal skills	
Knowledge of qualitative evaluation methods and materials	
Coordination skills	

